

MENU

My peer review records

+ Add a review

PEER REVIEW

GRANT REVIEW

PEER REVIEW INTEREST

Refine results

Quick filters

- Verified reviews
- Publicly displayed reviews
- Reviews with content
- Community reviews
- Web of Science Core Collection publications

Journals

Journal Research Field (ESI)

During Period

 to

Filter

43 peer review records of 39 manuscripts

Sort by: Date reviewed: newest first ▾

< 1 of 1 >

Multiple Disturbance Suppression of IPMSM Drives Based on Embedded Discrete-Time Repetitive ADRC with Optimized Parameter Selection
IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics

2023-10-21 [Edit](#) [Delete](#)

A FIR-Type Cell for Digitally Controlled LCL-filtered Inverters With Multi-cell Network
IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics

2023-08-11 [Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Performance Improvement Control for DC Microgrid Based on Model Predictive Control and Residual Generator
IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics

2023-03-15

A Robust Design Strategy for Resonant Controllers
Tuned above the LCL filter Resonance Frequency
IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics

2023-01-02 [Edit](#) [Delete](#)

MPPT Control Algorithm Based on Particle Swarm
Optimization and Adaptive Linear Linear active
disturbance rejection control

Energies

2022-11-24 [Edit](#) [Delete](#)

2022-11-12 [Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Robustness Improvement Strategy for a New
Predictive Controller

Electronics

2022-10-26 [Edit](#) [Delete](#)

An Improved Capacitor-Current-Feedback Active
Damping Based Control Method for LCL-Equipped
High-Speed PMSM

IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics

2022-07-22 [Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Back Electro Motive Force Estimation Method for
Cascade PI Control in Permanent Magnet
Synchronous Motors

IEEE Access

2021-11-06 [Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Modeling and Analysis of SOGI Based FLLs Using Dynamic Phasor Method

IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics

2021-10-30

[Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Back-Electro Motive Force Estimation Method for Cascade PI Control in Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors

IEEE Access

2021-10-13

[Edit](#) [Delete](#)

A Fractional-Order Model Predictive Control of Virtual Synchronous Generator to Enhance Frequency Dynamics in Islanded AC Microgrids

IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics

2021-09-12

[Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Three Phase PLL for Direct Per-Phase Information Acquisition

IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics

2021-08-01

[Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Position and Speed Estimation for PMSM Using Wideband Synchronous Fundamental-frequency Extraction Filter

IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion

2021-01-09

[Edit](#) [Delete](#)

[A Compensation Strategy of Flux Linkage Observer in SPMSM Sensorless Drives Based on Linear Extended State Observer](#)

14

Citations

IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion

2020-12-19

[Edit](#) [L 12 .e](#)

Current Regulator Designed in the Discrete-time Domain for Grid Connected Converters

IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics

2020-05-07

[Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Wide Frequency Band Single-Phase Amplitude and Phase Angle Detection Based on Integral and Derivative Actions

1
Citation

Electric Power Components and Systems

2020-04-02

[Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Axial Flux PM Generator with Fully Controlled Converter for Direct Driven Micro Wind Turbines

International Transactions on Electrical Energy Systems

2020-03-04

[Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Improved Non-Adaptive Demodulation Technique for Extraction of Grid Voltage Parameters

IET Generation, Transmission & Distribution

2020-03-02

[Edit](#) [Delete](#)

2019-12-03

[Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Current Regulator Designed in the Discrete-time Domain for Grid Connected Converters

IEEE Access

2020-01-13

[Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Resonant Frequency Analysis and System Stabilization of Shunt Active Power Filters with Multi-Proportional Resonant Indirect Current Control Methods when Compensating Capacitive Loads

IEEE Access

12

2019-12-24 [Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Wide Frequency Band Single-Phase Amplitude and Phase Angle Detection Based on Integral and Derivative Actions 1
Citation

IEEE Access

2019-10-17 [Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Dynamic data reconciliation to improve the result of controller performance assessment based on GMVC 6
Citation

IEEE Access

2019-10-05 [Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Stability Comparison and System Stabilization of Active Power Filters with Direct and Indirect Current Control Methods when Compensating Capacitive Loads

IEEE Access

2019-08-10 [Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Resonant Control of Power Converter Under Variable Frequency

International Transactions on Electrical Energy Systems

2019-07-26 [Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Resonant Control of Power Converter Under Variable Frequency

Electric Power Components and Systems

2019-03-23 [Edit](#) [Delete](#)

A Nonlinear Extended State Observer for Rotor Position and Speed Estimation for Sensorless IPMSM Drives 12
55
Citation

IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics

2019-01-12

[Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Advanced Position and Speed Extraction Using a Nonlinear Extended State Observer for Sensorless IPM Synchronous Motor Drives

IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics

2018-10-26

[Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Adaptive observer as single-phase PLL

IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics

2018-10-06

[Edit](#) [Delete](#)

An Observer-based Quadrature Signal Generator for Single-Phase PLL Synchronization

IEEE Power Electronics Letters

2018-09-23

[Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Current Harmonics Suppression of PMSM Based on Multiple Improved Complex Vector Proportional Integral Controllers

IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics

2018-08-16

[Edit](#) [Delete](#)

An Improved MRAS for Rotor Time Constant Updating in Induction Motor Drives Utilizing Dot Product of Stator Current and Rotor Flux ¹⁴ Citation

IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics

2018-05-17

[Edit](#) [Delete](#)

Optimized Full-Order Adaptive Observer Based Sensorless Induction Motor Control for Railway Traction System Under Low-Switching Frequency ¹²

IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics

2018-03-24

[Edit](#)

[Delete](#)

A Method for Realization of the Voltage Model Based on the Gopinath Model in Flux Observer for Rotor-Flux-Oriented Control of Induction Motors

IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics

2017-09-23

[Edit](#)

[Delete](#)

Stability Analysis of Generator-Excitation Control System With Time-Varying Delays

Electric Power Components and Systems

2017-08-18

[Edit](#)

[Delete](#)

Deadbeat Control Based on a Multipurpose Sliding Mode Disturbance Observer for Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors

IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion

2017-06-10

[Edit](#)

[Delete](#)

A Novel 3(n+1)-Switch Inverter Topology for Driving Three-Phase Loads Independently

IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics

2017-03-11

[Edit](#)

[Delete](#)

Torque-Ripple Reduction and Fast Torque Response Strategy for Torque Predictive Control of Induction Motors

IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics

2016-08-01

[Edit](#)

[Delete](#)

Improved Rotor Flux Estimation at Low Speeds for Torque MRAS-Based Sensorless Induction Motor Drives

12

80

Citation

IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion

2015-07-05 [Edit](#) [Delete](#)

2015-04-19 [Edit](#) [Delete](#)

© 2024
Clarivate
Training
Portal
Product
Support

Data
Correction
Privacy
Statement
Newsletter

Copyright
Notice
Cookie
Policy
Terms of
Use

[Manage
cookie
preferences](#)

Follow
Us